

Assessment of Deposit Money Banks on Financial Performance in Nigeria Banking System

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Abstract

This study investigated the deposit money banks' (DMBs) and financial performance in Nigeria during a 21-year span, from 2001 to 2021. The study specifically examined whether the bank size, monetary policy rate and inflation rate have a substantial impact on the financial performance of DMBs. Secondary data from the annual financial statements of eight chosen deposit money banks in Nigeria were used in the study. Panel regression analysis and ordinary least squares were used to thematically analyze the data that were produced. The study revealed that bank size has a significant negative impact on financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria, monetary policy rate do not exert any significant impact on the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria and inflationary pressures have no significant impact on the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria. Amongst other recommendations the study recommends that Bank size has a significant negative impact on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria. Banks should ensure they maintain capital adequacy and liquidity management to impact on bank performance.

Keywords: Deposit Money Bank, Bank size, inflation rate, monetary policy rate.

Introduction

The primary focus of the banking sector around the world is on taking deposits from the general public and using those deposits to lend to credit-worthy borrowers for investments, loans, and other purposes. Overdrafts, loans, advances, business funding agreements, local purchase order financing, etc. are all common forms of bank credit. Akinlo and Mofoluwaso (2014) observed that depository money banks' (DMBs) primary function is to give bank credit, also known as lending. Lending, which entails the risk that the borrower may not repay the loan as agreed, and paying a fixed rate of interest on term deposits, are two activities that make up the global banking industry. There is a chance that lending rates will decline, which would mean that the bank would earn less on investments than it would on deposits (Biabani, Gilaninia & Mohabatkhah, 2012).

The management of credit risk takes place in a setting that is unique to the banking sector and is both complex and unpredictable. However, banks provide loans and advances to people, businesses, and the government in order for them to carry out investments and other development activities. By doing this, banks help the economy expand and develop while also generating a profit that will meet shareholders' expectations. Unfortunately, DMB's profitability in Nigeria has been severely and adversely impacted for some time due to the steadily rising loan quality of assets, high levels of non-performing loans, and significant provisions for loan losses. The economic growth and efficiency of the economy are hampered by these NPLs (Karim, Chan & Hassan, 2010). In light of this, the work will assess the factors that contribute to non-performing loans and how they affect the profitability of DMBs in Nigeria from 2001 to 2021.

In order to conduct monetary policy inside an economy, Taiwan (2018) observes that monetary authorities employ the credit view and its sub-channels, the interest rate channel and the bank lending channel. For instance, an expansionary monetary policy that uses the interest channel would cut interest rates to lower the cost of capital, which would simultaneously raise investment and expenditure as well as aggregate demand and output. On the other hand, an expansionary monetary policy through the bank lending channel raises bank deposits and reserves, leading to a rise in the accessibility of bank loans, which promotes investment and consumer spending. This study is based on developing and putting into practice a viable framework for monetary policy which requires an understanding of the bank lending channel. According to Mishkin (2019), the foundation of the bank lending channel is the unique function that banks perform within the financial system in addressing issues with asymmetric information and other flaws in credit markets. Banks frequently act as financial middlemen who provide money to particular borrowers who lack access to credit markets. The magnitude of the external finance premium, which is the difference

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between the costs of a firm's externally generated funds (via issuing equity or debt) and its internally generated funds, reflects the imperfections (retained earnings). This implies that banks provide indirect finance while serving as financial mediators between SSUs and SDUs, building on their unique function in directing funds for productive use. According to Gambacorta and Mistrulli (2004), only big businesses issue commercial papers as a result, during monetary contractions, small and large enterprises display different behaviors, which minimizes the significance of the bank lending channel.

The contrasts between small and large businesses during monetary contractions typically do not cut against the bank lending perspective. In this regard, Kashyap, Stein and Wilcox (2013) noted that monetary authorities' contraction reduces the supply of loans to small businesses, and that small businesses expand their account payables in pursuit of alternative sources of financing. Large companies are simultaneously experiencing a surge in the demand for their account payables, which forces them to issue more commercial papers in order to secure additional external funding. Therefore, a rise in commercial papers would allow major companies to moderately and imperfectly replace banks' financial intermediation role. Despite the importance of the bank lending channel in directing capital toward productive uses, Kim and Sohn (2017) contend that loans do not play a crucial role since the initial impact of a monetary policy contraction on interest rates is felt through deposits rather than loans. In accordance with the banking theory of credit creation, this study challenges the claim made by the above scholars on the crucial function of loans, as banks do not lend existing money but instead generate new money.

Akinola (2022) investigated how bank size affected the financial results of listed deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The relationship between bank size and financial performance was also explored, as well as the moderating impact of adequate internal control. The study used an ex-post facto research strategy since secondary data were taken from 10 DMBs' published annual reports in Nigeria for the 12-year period between 2006 and 2017. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data (multiple regression analysis). According to the analysis's findings, the proxies for bank size (total assets, personnel count, and client deposits) all had a cumulative impact on return on asset for financial performance. Also, the effectiveness of internal controls as a moderating factor improved the impact of bank size on financial performance. The study came to the conclusion that the combination of total asset, personnel count, and client deposits, which served as proxies for bank size had an impact on financial performance.

Alfadhli and AlAli (2021) examined how Kuwaiti banks' financial performance was affected by their size. According to the study's analysis, the number of employees, the number of bank-owned branches, and customer deposits have a negative association with financial success, however shareholder ownership has a positive link. Kachumbo (2020) used panel data analysis to examine the factors influencing the financial performance of commercial Fintech banks in Kenya. The capital adequacy ratio, customer size, and the amount of loan advances given to customers served as proxies for the independent variable, and return on equity served as a proxy for the dependent variable. According to the findings, there is a negative and significant association between capital sufficiency and client volume and financial performance.

In their study of the financial performance of Kenya's quoted banks, Nyabaga and Wepukhulu (2020) examined the impact of business characteristics. The study's results utilizing regression analysis show that adequate capital and bank size have a considerable favorable impact on return on equity and return on asset. The return on equity and return on asset are negatively impacted by asset adequacy. Other studies operationalized financial performance using proxies like ROA and ROE (Aladwann, 2015; Jaouad & Lahsen, 2018). Only ROA was employed in this study as a stand-in for financial performance. The literature review is therefore founded on bank size and financial performance. Al-Homaidi, Tabash, Farhan and Almaqtari (2018), on the other hand, used a panel data analytic methodology to assess the effect of bank-specific characteristics on the profitability of 60 Indian banks. The results demonstrate that asset size and client deposits, which represent the size of the bank, had a favorable impact on profitability as evaluated by ROA and ROE. Using panel data from 43 banks from 2007 to 2016, Mwangi, Makau and Kosimbei (2014) determined the impact of bank size (total asset) on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study's findings demonstrated that total assets had a favorable impact on ROA and ROE. The study also discovered that a bank's financial performance increases with its size.

The study is grounded in agency theory because bank managers, who act as agents in this situation, may make self-serving decisions that could be detrimental to stockholder interests. Conflicts of interest and information asymmetry may arise because a variety of decisions impacting the resources of the principal's firm are delegated to the agents, according to agency theory (principal-agent dilemma). According to Rozina and Jewel (2017), when an agent chooses to act in his or her interests rather than that of their principal, this is known as a principal-agent issue (moral hazard). Due to the agent's insider trading and the control measures put in place by the principle to prevent the agent from pursuing personal interests, the principal is responsible for agency fees such as the costs incurred. Agency costs are necessary evils because they are less expensive than the costs associated with letting management pursue their own agenda at the expense of the primary. When one person (the

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2. Determine if monetary policy rate affected DMBs’ financial performance in Nigeria; and
3. Ascertain the extent to which inflation rate has impacted on DMBs’ financial performance.

Research Questions

The following research questions are thus posed by this study:

1. Does bank size have significant impact on DMBs’ financial performance in Nigeria?
2. Does monetary policy rate affect DMBs’ financial performance in Nigeria?
3. Does inflation rate have significant impact on DMBs’ financial performance in Nigeria?

Methodology

This study utilizes a longitudinal research design, which is based on the hypothesis that it will involve repeated observations of the same variables over the course of 21 years, from 2001 to 2021. The complete population of this study consists of the 19 recognized Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria that have been granted international and domestic authorization by the Central Bank of Nigeria. Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc are some of these as international authorizations. While the following deposit money institutions are authorized by the government: Citi Bank Nigeria Limited, Eco Bank Nigeria Plc, Heritage Bank Limited, Keystone Bank Limited, Polaris Bank Plc, Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc, Standard Chartered Bank Ltd, Sterling Bank Plc, Titan Trust Bank Limited, Unity Bank Plc, and Wema Bank Plc (CBN, 2021). The study adopts eight (8) international licensed deposit money banks as sample of the study out of the nineteen (19) deposit money banks in Nigeria for the period 2001 to 2021. These include Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa Plc and Zenith Bank Plc. This is due to their official annual data on the variables of the study can be accessed from the appropriate designated government agencies including the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and National Bureau of statistics (NBS) for the period covered by the study, 2001 to 2021. The case studies for the study were chosen using judgmental sampling approaches. The Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS) and Panel Data Regression techniques were utilized in the study to analyze the data. The eight (8) chosen banks were covered using panel data regression while the pooled OLS covered the individual variable data. The goal of the two methods is to compare their output. Additionally, panel data approach was used in the study. As a result, when discussing an estimator for the regression model’s coefficients, the term fixed effect estimator’ is employed. The fixed effect model is provided in its generalized form by;

$$Y_{it} = \delta_0 + \beta x_{it} + \mu_{it} + v_{it} \text{ ----- (i)}$$

Where;

Y_{it} = dependent variable

δ_0 = intercept

βx_{it} = vector of explanatory variable

μ_{it} = individual specific effect

v_{it} = error term

The Hausman Test was used to determine if the Fixed Effect Model or Random Effect Model is more appropriate for the investigation. The fixed effect model's generalized form is provided by;

$$Y_{it} = \delta + \beta x_{it} + \epsilon_i + \epsilon_{it} \text{ ----- (ii)}$$

Where;

ϵ_i = cross sectional error term

ϵ_{it} = individual observational error term

As a functional form of the following equations, the researchers propose the panel information model below:

MODEL 1

$$ROA = F(BKS, MPR, INF) \text{ ----- (iv)}$$

MODEL 11

$$ROE = F(BKS, MPR, INF) \text{ ----- (v)}$$

While the econometric form of the model is:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BKS_{it} + \beta_2 MPR_{it} + \beta_3 INF_{it} + e_{it} \text{ ----- (vi)}$$

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BKS_{it} + \beta_2 MPR_{it} + \beta_3 INF_{it} + e_{it} \text{ ----- (vii)}$$

i = cross-sectional variables from 1, 2, 3, -----21

t = time series variables from 1, 2, 3, -----21

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e = error term

Where;

ROA_{it} = Return on Assets of bank i at the end of year t proxy for bank performance.

ROE_{it} = Return on Equity of bank i at the end of year t proxy for bank performance.

BKS_{it} = Bank Size

MPR_{it} = Monetary policy rate

INF_{it} = Inflation rate

Inflation = $\frac{CCP\ Index - HCP\ Index}{CCP\ Index} \times 100$

Theoretical expectation is depicted as: $\beta_2, \beta_3 < 0$ and $\beta_1 > 0$

β_0 is to take care of the Constant Variable.

B_1 is the coefficient of Bank Size (BKS) which is expected to be greater than zero ($\beta_1 > 0$). That is a positive relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigeria is expected. B_2 is the coefficient of Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) which is expected to be less than zero ($\beta_2 < 0$). That is a negative relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigerian is expected. Finally, β_3 is the coefficient of Inflation Rate (INFL) which is expected to be less than zero ($\beta_3 < 0$). That is a negative relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigerian is expected.

This study uses Return on Assets and Return on Equity to capture its dependent variable depicting banks' performance in Nigeria. The measurement, for the calculation of Return on Assets is as follows:

$$ROA = \frac{\text{Net Profit After Tax}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

$$ROE = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Equity}}$$

While, the independent variables of this study can be measured thus:

1. Bank Size = Total Assets.
2. Monetary Policy Rate = Overnight rate banks charges one another to borrow funds.
3. Inflation Rate = $\frac{CCP\ Index - HCP\ Index}{CCP\ Index} \times 100$.

Results

Question 1

To what extent is the influence of bank size, monetary policy rate and inflation rate on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria (ROA)?

Table 1: Panel Regression Result for the ROA Equation

Variable	<i>Fixed effects</i>				<i>Random effects</i>			
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
Constant	10.534	0.00	8.965	0.00	8.952	0.02	7.504	0.05
BKS	-0.920	0.00	-0.875	0.00	-0.838	0.01	-0.754	0.02
MPR	-0.046	0.27	-0.046	0.27	-0.073	0.53	-0.076	0.49
INFL	-0.035	0.29	-0.001	0.97	0.021	0.82	0.037	0.67
R-sq.	0.634		0.66		0.062		0.085	
Adj. R-sq.	0.603		0.63		0.027		0.045	
F-stat.	21.502		20.49157		1.761		2.134	

Source: Author's computations

It can be seen that the goodness of fit statistics has improved drastically over the pooled OLS estimates in each of the estimations. The goodness of fit statistics values is also better in the fixed effects estimates than in the random effect's estimates. The adjusted R-squared value in the fixed effects estimates shows that about 60 percent of systematic variations in ROA for the banks are captured in the model with control, while 63 percent is captured in the model without control. Thus, the focus of the analysis in this study is on fixed effect estimations. The focus is on the particular contribution of the individual variables to return on asset (ROA) of the banks.

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Question 2

To what extent is the influence of bank size, monetary policy rate and inflation rate on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria (ROE)?

Table 2: Panel Regression result for the ROA equation

Variable	Fixed Effects				Random Effects			
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
C	0.985	0.00	0.947	0.00	1.152	0.06	1.171	0.07
BKS	-0.030	0.09	-0.025	0.16	0.022	0.67	0.021	0.69
MPR	-0.008	0.22	-0.008	0.22	-0.011	0.54	-0.011	0.54
INFL	0.004	0.39	0.005	0.32	0.014	0.33	0.014	0.35
R-squared	0.469		0.473		0.144		0.144	
Adj.R-squared	0.425		0.425		0.112		0.106	
F-statistic	10.476		9.806		4.505		3.840	

Source: Author’s computations

The adjusted R-squared values for the fixed effects estimates are also larger than those of the pooled OLS and the random effects estimates. This again justifies the efficiency of the fixed effects approach to the estimation for this study. The important focus of the analysis is on the coefficients of the explanatory variables. The coefficient of both monetary policy rate and inflation rate also fail the significance tests at the 5 percent level. This shows that, just like ROA, the external macroeconomic factors do not have significant impact on the return to equity of DMBS in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This finding support previous studies by Olaoluwa and Shomade (2017) and Kim and Sohn (2017) where the role of interest rate was demonstrated to be more related to deposits rather than to loans in the Nigerian and developed country context. In the same vein, inflation rate was found to have no impact on financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria. Thus, external or macroeconomic factors do not explain the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria, especially in terms of ROA. This outcome is crucial and shows that financial performances of banks in Nigeria are essentially disconnected from macroeconomic occurrences in the country. In particular, the result indicates that whether the banks charge higher or lower interest rates, the operational efficiency of the banks do not change significantly.

Moreover, rising price level in the economy (or economic instability) also do not influence the financial profitability of the banks. This outcome portends both positive and negative implications. In the first place, it shows that banks in Nigeria may not necessarily fail or run into serious balance sheet even when inflationary pressures are high. Thus, these banks appear to be effectively shielded from the external macroeconomic factors in terms of their operational activities. On the other hand, this result suggests that the banking system is not linked to the real sector in Nigeria. Thus, when the real sector is facing price decimation, the banking system, which is expected to bear the brunt of the real sector financial woes, is not essentially affected. Thus, the banking system does not appear to be playing its financial roles effectively in the economy.

Conclusion

Though banks offer many services, most of them are related to credit and cash management which are critical aspects of liquidity among the banks. A major risk of systemic failure is characterized by the rate of non-performing loans in the banking system. Thus, proper focus on its main activities from both the policy and operational perspectives are essential. These perspectives particularly involve appropriate strategies for the management of lending activities that are geared towards contributing greatly to bank performance, productivity and long run stability of the system. In this study, the role of deposit money banks and other related aspects of the banking system in Nigeria were examined in relation to their impacts on the financial performance of these banks. It has been shown that indeed, bank size has a significant negative impact on financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria, monetary policy rate do not exert any significant impact on the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria and inflationary pressures have no significant impact on the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered:

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1. Bank size has a significant negative impact on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria. Banks should ensure they maintain capital adequacy and liquidity management to impact on bank performance.
2. Monetary policy rate adopted by Central Bank through its prudential guidelines must make sure that their monetary policies measures address the financial system in order to influence bank performance. From the foregoing the regulatory agencies in Nigeria have more responsibilities to carry out in terms of guiding the banks in their loan policies and operations more properly. It is known that much dependence on loan strategies that are high-risk tends to result in higher loan defaults in the banking system. Hence, the regulatory agencies need to regulate the lending visa-visa the deposit and liquidity stance of banks on a regular basis.
3. Government through central banks should embark on fiscal/monetary policies that targets reduction of high inflation rate through adoption of contractionary/expansionary measures.

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